

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number ③ - ⑤a

Progress of Excavation SURFACE ③ cleaned after ④d Removed
⑤ Removed to Section E-W cutting irregular Depression that ⑤
apparently intentionally (?) fills and to E, W Balbs. E-W
Section across floor depression w/ gypsum ⑤ fill drawn.
⑤a Sampled

Locus Description ③ - WHITE BUFF GYPSUM (adhering to floor)
⑤a BUFF GYPSUM (adhering to N edge (vertical) face) of
pillar socket. Sampled

Location in Square ③ Adhering to floor under 4-4d N of
pillar socket ⑤a Adhering to vertical N face pillar socket,
W side trench.

Under Locus 4d MOTTLED BROWN SAND Over Locus STONE RUBBLE - GYPSUM

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels 7.89, 7.86, 7.87.

Analysis of non-artifactual materials ③ 3 small chips Polerite
⑤a In little taken out to form section against face pillar
socket, several small granite frags - 1 possible dalerite